

YUQORI SEZGIR BO'YOQLI QUYOSH ELEMENTLARI (DSSC)NI TAYYORLASH TEKNOLOGIYASI VA ISHLASH PRINTSIPI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu ishda yuqori sezgir bo'yoqli quyosh elementlari (DSSC- Dye sensitized solar cell) ni tayyorlash texnologiyasi va uni ishlash printsipi tadqiq qilingan. Bu quyosh elementlarini tayyorlash uchun ishlatiladigan materiallar va undagi qatlamlarni tayyorlash texnologiyasi keltirilgan. DSSC larda elektr zaryadini, elektr potentsialini va elektr tokini hosil bo'lishi tadqiq qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar. Yuqori sezgir bo'yoqli quyosh elementlari (DSSC- Dye sensitized solar cell), fotoelektrod, konturelektrod, fotoanod, elektrolit, gel polimer elektrolit (GPE), yorug'likka yuqori sezgir bo'yoq.

ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ ПРИГОТОВЛЕНИЯ И ПРИНЦИП РАБОТЫ СЕНСИБИЛИЗИРОВАННЫЙ КРАСИТЕЛЕМ СОЛНЕЧНЫХ ЭЛЕМЕНТОВ (DSSC)

Аннотация. В настоящей работе исследована технология приготовления и принцип работы, сенсibilizированный красителем солнечных элементов (DSSC). Представлены материалы понадобившейся для приготовления и технология приготовления слоёв этого солнечного элемента. Исследованы образования электрического заряда, электрического потенциала и электрического тока в DSSC

Ключевые слова. Сенсibilizированный красителем солнечные элементы (DSSC- Dye sensitized solar cell), фотоэлектрод, контурэлектрод, фотоанод, электролит, гель полимерный электролит, высокочувствительный к свету.

TECHNOLOGY OF PREPARATION AND THE PRINCIPLE OF OPERATION DYE SENSITIZED SOLAR CELLS (DSSC)

Annotation. In this experiment, we have examined the working mechanism of a dye sensitized solar cells (DSSC) and its technologies. Moreover, we included necessary materials to make solar cells and its layers. Apart from that, we have researched electric current, electric potential and how to generate electricity.

Keywords. Dye sensitized solar cells (DSSC), photoelectrode, contourelectrode, photoanode, electrolyte, gel polymer electrolyte, highly sensitive to light.

Introduction. Currently, the energy consumed in the world is mainly energy obtained from fossil fuels, that is, thermal energy, nuclear energy, and hydropower. However, the limited amount of such fuels, they are not ecologically clean, and they are not seismically stable [1]. For

this reason, modern demands place before mankind the use of renewable and environmentally friendly energy sources, that is, solar and wind energy.

Thermal energy of solar radiation is used in heating systems, solar energy is converted into electrical energy in semiconductor-based solar cells and photoelectrochemical solar cells. Using chemical combinations (reactions), substances that can be used as fuel are being created [2].

Methodology. Materials used in the manufacture of DSSC solar cells: We used the following chemicals and solutions to prepare DSSC solar cells. In the preparation of the solar cell electrodes, we used titanium dioxide (TiO₂) P90 with a molecular size of 15 nm and (TiO₂) P25 with a molecular size of 21 nm, polyethylene glycol (PEG), Triton-X100, fluorine-doped tin oxide grown glass (FTO), and platinum (Pt) from Supelco Analytical, USA, developed by Sigma Aldrich. Polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA), polyethylene oxide PEO, dimethylformamide (DMF), 98% pure ethylene carbonate (EC), 99% pure propylene carbonate (PC), tetrapropylammonioiodide (TPAI), and iodine (I₂) were used in the preparation of the electrolyte. As a dye, we used Ruthenium Ru (Ruthenizer) 535, developed by the US company Supelco Analytical. Solutions developed in Malaysia: 69% pure nitric acid (HNO₃) with a pH=1 dissolved in 99.5% pure ethanol (C₂H₅OH).

Results and Discussion. Preparation of gel polymer electrolyte (GPE). This electrolyte has been used in the production of solar cells. To prepare the gel polymer electrolyte (GPE): polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA), iodine (I₂) and tetrapropylammonium iodide (TPAI) are dried under vacuum before use. Then, 0.02 g of polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA), 0.02 g of polyethylene oxide (PEO), 0.25 g of ethylene carbonate (EC), 0.25 g of propylene carbonate (PC), and 0.02 g of dimethylformamide (DMF) are prepared, as well as tetrapropylammonium iodide (TPAI) and iodine (I₂) in the amounts indicated in Table 1. First, polyethylene oxide (PEO) and polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) were mixed in the given amounts with dimethylformamide (DMF) solvent and stirred at a temperature of 373 K until the mixture became homogeneous. Then, ethylene carbonate (EC) and propylene carbonate (PC) were added to the mixture in the given amounts, and tetrapropylammonium iodide (TPAI) was added separately in the amounts indicated in Table 1, and the mixture was stirred again at 373 K. After the mixture was cooled to room temperature, 10% iodine (I₂) powder in tetrapropylammonium iodide (TPAI) was added and stirred for several minutes until homogeneous.

The following table shows the compositional amounts of tetrapropylammonium iodide (TPAI) and iodine (I₂) in various electrolytes:

Table 1.

Sample name	TPAI m _{um} , %	TPAI, rp	I ₂ , rp
H1	8,33	0,05	0,005
H2	16,67	0,1	0,01
H3	25	0,15	0,015
H4	33,3	0,2	0,02
H5	41,67	0,25	0,025

Electrolytes play a crucial role in charge transport in DSSCs. The electrolyte must contain a redox couple to carry electrons from the electrode (cathode) to the ionized dye at the

photoanode [3]. For efficient charge transfer, the energy of free electrons must match the Fermi level of the TiO_2 layer. In this work, the I-/I-3 pair was chosen for use in the electrolyte due to its many advantages described in the literature. [4].

The most commonly used electrolytes in DSSCs are liquids, but gel polymer electrolytes (GPE) are currently being used in these solar cells [5]. The use of gel polymer electrolytes (GPE) in the manufacture of DSSC solar cells avoids the problems associated with the use of liquid electrolytes, such as electrode corrosion and evaporation of liquid electrolytes. In addition, GPEs provide good contact with the electrodes, have higher ionic conductivity than solid polymer electrolytes, and polymer electrolytes ensure the long-term physical and chemical stability of DSSCs.

Conclusion. Thus, in this work, the manufacturing technology and operating principle of highly sensitive dye-sensitized solar cells (DSSC) were studied. It is clear that the manufacturing technology of this solar cell is simple and inexpensive, and we recommend its adoption in Uzbekistan.

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